

Methods for Developing Skills in Independent Execution of General Development Exercises

B. Y. Khaydarov¹

¹ Senior Lecturer, Department of Types of Sports Activities, FarDU

Abstract:

This article analyzes methods for developing skills in the independent execution of general development exercises. The study provides a detailed review of key approaches and methodologies for enhancing skills in independent work. It describes methods for assigning purposeful exercises to students, time management, planning, and improving efficiency. The importance of consistent feedback and individualized approaches is highlighted, along with methods for supporting independent work through exercises tailored to students' personal interests and group activities. The article proposes methodological approaches necessary for increasing student motivation and ensuring effectiveness in developing independent work skills.

Keywords: independent execution, primary school students, general development exercises, didactic tools, qualification, skill, homework.

Methods for developing skills in the independent execution of general development exercises are crucial for reinforcing the physical activity of primary school students and improving their success in the educational process. By encouraging students to independently engage in exercises through these methods, it is possible to positively impact their overall health and learning activities. Based on research by scholars on teaching primary school students to independently perform general development exercises, the following characteristics have been identified:

1. The social-pedagogical significance of fostering students' independence in their learning activities should be considered.
2. The psychological and didactic theoretical foundations of skills should be identified.
3. Didactic tools for organizing the development of skills in independent learning should be developed.

4. The core of developing independent work skills in primary school students involves teachers familiarizing themselves with and thoroughly mastering new methodological systems and instructional recommendations.

Based on this proposed concept, the methodology for developing skills in independent learning systems in primary school students has been established. To achieve this goal, a system of special exercises analyzed from both theoretical and practical perspectives has been developed.

When examining methods for developing the skills necessary for performing general physical development exercises independently, it is important to emphasize that independent physical education for primary school students holds significant importance in contemporary physical education methodology.

In physical education classes, teachers allocate ample time for students to perform physical exercises independently after class. Additionally, the basic elements of the exercises learned during the lesson are assigned as homework for students to practice. To instill a sense of responsibility in students for their physical education, it is essential that they regularly engage in general physical development exercises on their own. This practice enhances the students' educational and cognitive activities, strengthens their health, and overall improves both their digestive system and muscle function. Consequently, students are able to start their lessons or homework and other activities with enthusiasm and maintain a positive mood.

To ensure that primary school students do not experience excessive fatigue during school lessons and to increase the pace of their educational and cognitive activities, there is an excellent opportunity to incorporate general physical development exercises. After each lesson, students should independently perform general physical exercises for 5-8 minutes in fresh air or in a classroom with adequate ventilation, rather than merely doing simple swaying or comfortable sitting, which is more beneficial.

Primary school students should engage in general physical development exercises either individually or in small groups of three or slightly more. Researchers and experienced teachers emphasize that performing these exercises in groups is more effective than individual practice.

Teaching primary school students to gather with themselves and their peers after class fosters the development of orderly and systematic study habits, rest, and work ethics. The effectiveness of a student's studies, knowledge, work, and other activities in life is closely linked to their health. Such education provides a reliable foundation for preparing students to become true patriots.

It is well known that in the process of developing the ability of primary school students to independently perform general developmental exercises, certain critical requirements are established from a didactic perspective.

In Figure 1, these requirements are depicted as an interconnected and evolving process.

Figure 1 - System of Didactic Requirements for Independent Performance of General Developmental Exercises by Primary School Students

At this point, let us elaborate on these didactic requirements. The focus is on reinforcing the educational trajectory of physical education lessons that teach general developmental exercises and on developing the capability for continuous independent performance.

By introducing techniques for independent work and evaluation of other students' activities into the content of the tasks given to students, the instructive nature of the lesson improves. After explaining the educational tasks in the lesson, each physical education teacher should allow students to assist each other while performing exercises in pairs.

In this context, it is possible to permit students to assume the role of teaching assistants and provide instructions for group exercises. The teacher must select and utilize practical tasks that are necessary for forming students' skills in addressing specific educational tasks. Let us examine the process of forming group exercise skills in accordance with the level of independent performance skills. For instance, let us analyze some tasks from the system of general developmental exercises for primary school students.

Firstly, attention should be paid to the formation of educational skills in the performance and execution process of general developmental exercises.

Task 1: Calculating with the instructor during exercise. The conformity of the performed actions is assessed through self-calculation.

Task 2: Classification of errors made by the instructor during the exercise. Indicate where errors occurred in explanations, presentations, and calculations.

Task 3: Independently select types of exercises as an instructor and perform them in a group. Evaluation will consider how well the instructions were explained, the initial norms demonstrated, and the accuracy of the commands given.

By completing these educational tasks, a system of knowledge and skills necessary for students to independently perform general developmental exercises is established.

In conclusion, it can be said that, to develop independent performance skills, students should first be provided with clear goals and tasks that enable them to work autonomously. Teaching students to manage their time, plan, and work efficiently will encourage independent work. Various exercises and tests can be used to develop students' skills in independent thinking and problem-solving. Regular and consistent feedback aids students in analyzing and improving their work. When forming independent performance skills, an individualized approach and exercises tailored to personal interests are of significant importance. Supporting independent work through collaboration, group work, and discussions provides additional motivation for students.

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